

A FUZZY TIME SERIES FORECASTING METHOD FOR PREDICTION BASED ON RICE PRODUCTION

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Abstract:

The work presented in this paper is a contribution to modeling and demand forecasting in a rice production. By using a time series approach, our work demonstrates how historical demand data can be used to predict the future demand and how these predictions affect the supply chain. In this paper, the suitability of developed model has also been examined in the crop production forecasting by implementing it on historical time series data of rice production of farm (India) and the obtained forecasted values have been compared with the Computational Method using various means Arithmetic Mean, Geometric Mean and Harmonic Mean.

1. Introduction:

Forecasting has always been a crucial challenge for managers and scientists to arrive accurate decisions. Time-series analysis is an important tool for forecasting the future in terms of past history. Time-series methods are generally used when there is not much information about the generation process of the underlying variable and when other variables provide no clear explanation of the studied variable. A recent review of the literature on time series forecasting is considered by [2, 3]. Many techniques for time-series analysis have been developed assuming linear relationships among the series variables. On the other hand, in many manufacturing and services industries, because of lacking sufficient historical data, traditional time series forecasting methods do not usually make reasonable judgments, so that there are large margins of errors between the predictive and actual values. To solve this problem, Song and Chissom first proposed the concept of fuzzy time series. The main property of the fuzzy time series is that the values of the demand variables are linguistic values. The forecast section of the forecast data is analyzed with forecast stock, temperature, foreign exchange daily price, crop production, education enrolment (Song and Chissom) [1]. The properties and definitions of the fuzzy time series are defined in Zaeh [4]. When handling predictions based on fuzzy time sequences, the length of the intervals is very important, which greatly affects the predictive accuracy ratio (Song and Chissom) [2, 3]. The computational method gave better results by comparing time variation with fuzzy time sequences [5-7].

2. Fuzzy Time Series:

Definition 2.1:

Let U be the universe of discourse, where $U = \{g_i\}_{i=1}^n$. A fuzzy set F_i in the universe of discourse U is defined as follows:

$$F_i = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{M_{F_i}(g_i)}{g_i}, \text{ Where } M_{F_i} \text{ is the membership function of the fuzzy set } F_i, M_{F_i}: U \rightarrow [0,1], M_{F_i}(g_j) \text{ is the degree of membership of } g_j \text{ in the fuzzy set } F_i, M_{F_i}(g_j) \in [0,1] \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq n.$$

Let $X(t) (t = \dots, 0, 1, 2, \dots)$ be the universe of discourse in which fuzzy sets $F_i(t) (i = 1, 2, \dots)$ are defined in the universe of discourse $X(t)$. Assume that $M(t)$ is a collection of $F_i(t) (i = 1, 2, \dots)$, then $M(t)$ is called a fuzzy time series of $X(t) (t = \dots, 0, 1, 2, \dots)$.

Definition 2.2:

Assume that there is a fuzzy relationship $FR(t-1, t)$, such that $M(t) = M(t-1) \circ FR(t-1, t)$, where the symbol " $\circ$ " represents the max-min composition operator, then $M(t)$ is called caused by $M(t-1)$. The relation FR is called first order model of $M(t)$.

Further, if fuzzy relation $FR(t, t-1)$ of $M(t)$ is independent of time t , that is to say for different times t_1 and t_2 , $FR(t_1, t_1-1) = FR(t_2, t_2-1)$, then $M(t)$ is called a time invariant fuzzy time series.

Definition 2.3:

Let $M(t-1) = F_i$ and let $M(t) = F_j$, where F_i and F_j are fuzzy sets, then the FLR between $M(t-1)$ and $M(t)$ can be denoted by $F_i \rightarrow F_j$, where F_i and F_j are called the left-hand side (LHS) and the right hand side (RHS) of the FLR, respectively [5].

Definition 2.4:

FLR having the same left-hand side can be grouped into a FLR Group. For example, assume that the following FLR

exist:

$$F_i \rightarrow F_{ja}, F_i \rightarrow F_{jb}, F_i \rightarrow F_{jc}, \dots, F_i \rightarrow F_{jm}$$

3. Fuzzy Time Series Forecasting Method Using Different Mean Techniques [6]:

Step 1:

The universe of discourse is considered as $U = [V_{min} - \alpha, V_{max} + \beta]$ into intervals of equal length, where V_{min} and V_{max} are the minimum value and the maximum value of the historical data, respectively. α and β are two proper positive real values to divide the universe of discourse U into n intervals $l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n$ of equal length.

Step 2:

The universe of discourse $U = [400, 1100]$, $F_1, F_2, \dots, \text{and } F_7$ are linguistic terms represented by fuzzy sets. where $l_1 = [400, 500]$, $l_2 = [500, 600]$, $l_3 = [600, 700]$, $l_4 = [700, 800]$, $l_5 = [800, 900]$, $l_6 = [900, 1000]$ and $l_7 = [1000, 1100]$;

Step 3:

Define the linguistic terms A_i represented by fuzzy sets, shown as follows:

$$F_1 = \sum_{i=1}^7 \frac{M_{F_1}(g_i)}{l_i}, M_{F_1}(g_1) = 1, M_{F_1}(g_2) = 0.5, M_{F_1}(g_i) = 0, i = 3,4,5,6,7.$$

$$F_2 = \sum_{i=1}^7 \frac{M_{F_2}(g_i)}{l_i}, M_{F_2}(g_1) = 0.5, M_{F_2}(g_2) = 1, M_{F_2}(g_3) = 0.5, M_{F_2}(g_4) = 0.5, M_{F_2}(g_5) = 0.5, M_{F_2}(g_6) = 0.5, M_{F_2}(g_7) = 0.5, i = 4,5,6,7$$

$$F_7 = \sum_{i=1}^7 \frac{M_{F_7}(g_i)}{l_i}, M_{F_7}(g_6) = 0.5, M_{F_7}(g_7) = 1, M_{F_7}(g_i) = 0, i = 1,2,3,4,5.$$

Where $F_1, F_2, \dots$ and F_7 are linguistic terms represented by fuzzy sets $F_1 = \sum_{i=1}^7 \frac{M_{F_1}(g_i)}{l_i}, M_{F_1}(g_1) = 1, M_{F_1}(g_2) = 0.5, M_{F_1}(g_i) = 0, i = 3,4,5,6,7. F_2 = \sum_{i=1}^7 \frac{M_{F_2}(g_i)}{l_i}, M_{F_2}(g_1) = 0.5, M_{F_2}(g_2) = 1, M_{F_2}(g_3) = 0.5, M_{F_2}(g_4) = 0.5, M_{F_2}(g_5) = 0.5, M_{F_2}(g_6) = 0.5, M_{F_2}(g_7) = 0.5, i = 4,5,6,7.$

Step 4:

Assume that the fuzzified data of the i th year is F_j and assume that there is only one fuzzy logical relationship in the fuzzy logical relationship groups in which the current state of the fuzzy logical relationship is F_j , shown as follows: “ $F_j \rightarrow F_k$ ”

Where F_j and F_k are fuzzy sets and the maximum membership value of F_k occurs at interval l_k , then the forecasted data of the $i + 1$ th year is the midpoint m_k of the interval l_k .

Step 5: Rules for Forecasting

- p_j - Lower value of l_j , q_j - Upper value of l_j , l - length of l_j
- The Midpoint m_k of l_k , c_n - value of state n , $[x]$ - largest integer value
- a_j - Arithmetic Mean of forecasted value of the current state ‘ j ’
- b_j - Geometric Mean of forecasted value of the current state ‘ j ’
- c_j - Harmonic Mean of forecasted value of the current state ‘ j ’

Fuzzy Time Series Forecasting Algorithms:

Obtained fuzzy logical relation for $F_j \rightarrow F_k, c = 0$ and $x = 0$

For $i = 3, 4, \dots$ (End of time series data)

1. $d_n = |(c_n - 2c_{n-1} + c_{n-2})|$
2. i) if $m_j + d_n/6 \geq p_k$ & $m_j + d_n/6 \leq q_k$ then $c = c + m_j + d_n/6, x = x + 1$
 ii) if $m_j - d_n/6 \geq p_k$ & $m_j - d_n/6 \leq q_k$ then $c = c + m_j - d_n/6, x = x + 1$
 iii) if $m_j + d_n/4 \geq p_k$ & $m_j + d_n/4 \leq q_k$ then $c = c + m_j + d_n/4, x = x + 1$
 iv) if $m_j - d_n/4 \geq p_k$ & $m_j - d_n/4 \leq q_k$ then $c = c + m_j - d_n/4, x = x + 1$
 v) if $m_j + d_n/2 \geq p_k$ & $m_j + d_n/2 \leq q_k$ then $c = c + m_j + d_n/2, x = x + 1$
 vi) if $m_j - d_n/2 \geq p_k$ & $m_j - d_n/2 \leq q_k$ then $c = c + m_j - d_n/2, x = x + 1$
 vii) if $m_j + d_n \geq p_k$ & $m_j + d_n \leq q_k$ then $c = c + m_j + d_n, x = x + 1$
 viii) if $m_j - d_n \geq p_k$ & $m_j - d_n \leq q_k$ then $c = c + m_j - d_n, x = x + 1$
 ix) if $m_j + 2d_n \geq p_k$ & $m_j + 2d_n \leq q_k$ then $c = c + m_j + 2d_n, x = x + 1$
 x) if $m_j - 2d_n \geq p_k$ & $m_j - 2d_n \leq q_k$ then $c = c + m_j - 2d_n, x = x + 1$
 xi) if $m_j + 3d_n \geq p_k$ & $m_j + 3d_n \leq q_k$ then $c = c + m_j + 3d_n, x = x + 1$
 xii) if $m_j - 3d_n \geq p_k$ & $m_j - 3d_n \leq q_k$ then $c = c + m_j - 3d_n, x = x + 1$
3. $a_k = [(c + m_k) / (x + 1) + 0.5]$,
 $b_k = [(c * m_k)^{1/(x + 1)} + 0.5]$
 $c_k = [(x + 1) * c * m_k / (c + m_k) + 0.5]$

Next i

4. Example:

Table 1: Historical time series data of Rice Production of Farm (India)

S.No	Year	AV	S.No	Year	AV
1	1981	1025	13	1993	994
2	1982	512	14	1994	759
3	1983	1005	15	1995	883
4	1984	852	16	1996	599
5	1985	440	17	1997	499
6	1986	502	18	1998	590
7	1987	775	19	1999	911

8	1988	465	20	2000	862
9	1989	795	21	2001	801
10	1990	970	22	2002	1067
11	1991	742	23	2003	917
12	1992	635			

AV - Actual Value (Production) (kg/ha)

Table 2: Fuzzy Linguistic Values of Rice Production

S.No	Year	AV	FLV	S.No	Year	AV	FLV
1	1981	1025	A ₇	13	1993	994	A ₆
2	1982	512	A ₂	14	1994	759	A ₄
3	1983	1005	A ₇	15	1995	883	A ₅
4	1984	852	A ₅	16	1996	599	A ₂
5	1985	440	A ₁	17	1997	499	A ₁
6	1986	502	A ₂	18	1998	590	A ₂
7	1987	775	A ₄	19	1999	911	A ₆
8	1988	465	A ₁	20	2000	862	A ₅
9	1989	795	A ₄	21	2001	801	A ₅
10	1990	970	A ₆	22	2002	1067	A ₇
11	1991	742	A ₄	23	2003	917	A ₆
12	1992	635	A ₃				

FLV - Fuzzy Linguistic Value

$$\text{MSE (Mean Square Error)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |FV_i - AV_i|^2}{n} \text{ and } \text{FE(\%)} = (|FV - AV|/AV) \times 100$$

Here FE - Forecasted Error, FV - Forecasted Value, AV - Actual Value

Average Forecasting Error (AFE) = Sum of FE/Number of Errors

5. Fuzzy Logical Relationship of Rice Production:

- A₇→A₂, A₂→A₇, A₇→A₅, A₅→A₁, A₁→A₂,
- A₂→A₄, A₄→A₁, A₁→A₄, A₄→A₆, A₆→A₄,
- A₄→A₃, A₃→A₆, A₆→A₄, A₄→A₅, A₅→A₂,
- A₂→A₁, A₁→A₂, A₂→A₆, A₆→A₅, A₅→A₅,
- A₅→A₇, A₇→A₆

Table 3: Forecasted Value of Different Means of Rice Production

S.No	Year	AV	a	b	c
1	1981	1025	-	-	-
2	1982	512	-	-	-
3	1983	1005	-	-	-
4	1984	852	850	914.2	840.2
5	1985	440	450	445.3	444.5
6	1986	502	541.4	544.8	538
7	1987	775	750	766.3	742
8	1988	465	450	447.2	423.5
9	1989	795	750	735.2	727
10	1990	970	950	928.3	924.3
11	1991	742	750	770.7	746
12	1992	635	658.3	658.8	640.1
13	1993	994	974	948.7	954.6
14	1994	759	746	731.8	724.1
15	1995	883	851.3	863.9	839.4
16	1996	994	550	547.7	523.8
17	1997	759	444.5	457.3	433.2
18	1998	883	553.9	543.5	519.6
19	1999	599	950	939.2	915
20	2000	499	858.7	857.5	845.5
21	2001	590	833.3	848.5	854
22	2002	911	1050	1048.8	1024.4
23	2003	862	957.3	957.8	945.3
Average Error			3.82	4.61	5.23
MSE			913.62	1380.25	1816.7

Table 4: Mean Square Error of Different Methods of Rice Production

Methods	a-FL(AM)	b-FL(GM)	c-FL(HM)	Singh Method [6]	Chen Method [7]
Average Error	3.82	4.61	5.23	4.23	21.08
MSE	913.62	1380.25	1816.7	1140.13	28200.71

Figure 1: Comparison Fuzzy Forecasted Value of Different Means

6. Conclusion:

The model that we selected and which minimizes the MSE (913.62) based on Arithmetic Mean compared with other means based on Geometric Mean (1816.7) and Harmonic Mean (28200.71). The result obtained proves that this model can be used for modeling and forecasting the future demand in this rice production; these findings will offer guidance for future rice production in terms of decision-making.

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